

THE RELEVANCE OF ADAPTING STUDENTS OF THE XXI-ST CENTURY TO THE NEW REALITIES OF STUDYING AT UNIVERSITIES

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Annotatsiya. Bu ish XXI asr talabalarimizni O‘zbekiston oliy o‘quv yurtlaridagi darslarga moslashtirishning dolzarbligiga bag‘ishlangan. Talabalar katta axborot resurslariga ega, ular universitetda o‘qish davomida ko‘plab muammolarni mustaqil ravishda hal qila oladilar, lekin ular buni har doim ham zarur deb hisoblamaydilar. Shu maqsadda turli xil strategiyalardan foydalanish mumkin, ular stressli vaziyatlarning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari va shaxsning individual xususiyatlari bilan belgilanadi. Ushbu yengish strategiyalarini bir qator belgilarga ko‘ra tasniflashga urinishlar qilingan. Tadqiqot shuningdek, talabalar shaxsiyatining sub'ektiv tomonlari haqidagi tushunchamizni kengaytirishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: moslashish, stressli vaziyat, kognitiv strategiya, english strategiyalarining tasnifi, rejalashtirish strategiyasi

Аннотация. Настоящая работа посвящена актуальности адаптации наших студентов XXI века к занятиям в высших учебных заведениях Узбекистана. Студенты обладают огромными ресурсами информации, они способны решать множество задач в процессе обучения в вузе самостоятельно, но не всегда считают нужным это делать. Для этого могут быть использованы различные стратегии, которые определяются спецификой стрессогенных ситуаций и индивидуальными характеристиками человека. Были предприняты попытки классифицировать эти коупинг-стратегии по ряду признаков.

Также исследование позволяет расширить наши представления о субъектных аспектах личности студентов.

Ключевые слова: адаптация, стрессовая ситуация, когнитивная стратегия, классификация коупинг-стратегий, стратегия планирования

Abstract. This work is devoted to the relevance of the adaptation of our students of the 21st century to studies in higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan. Students have huge resources of information, they are able to solve many problems in the process of studying at the university independently, but do not always consider it necessary to do so. For this, various strategies can be used, which are determined by the specifics of stressful situations and individual characteristics of a person. Attempts were made to classify these coping strategies according to a number of features. The study also allows us to expand our understanding of the subjective aspects of the personality of students.

Key words: adaptation, stressful situation, cognitive strategy, classification of coping strategies, planning strategy.

Nowadays, university students have high demands for education, but they themselves are not ready to work hard to get the higher education, to use their school skills and abilities to the maximum, to invest this knowledge in a comparatively new area of acquiring scientific knowledge, to implement their creative potential in practice in their chosen profession.

The new environment of the university education process also presupposes a certain stereotype of students' behavior, but not all students understand this. Today, the higher education system of Uzbekistan has undergone crucial changes. Some positive reforms have a negative effect in the students' minds. Students consider the shortened classroom lectures period and the release of the 6th school day for independent study as their personal time for rest. This is one of the reasons why students cannot cope with the academic and emotional burden of their new status. They must master many unfamiliar and unexpected aspects of the university learning process. This is far from being easy for everyone.

The theory of coping with difficult life situations arose in the second half of the twentieth century, however, it is extremely significant today. The term was introduced by the American scientist Abraham Maslow. By "coping" we mean constantly changing cognitive and behavioral attempts to cope with specific external and/or internal demands that are assessed as stress or exceed the student's ability to cope with them. These demands have not lost their relevance and are becoming even more urgent in the age of globalization today.

Coping behavior is a form of behavior that reflects the person's readiness to solve life's problems. This behavior is aimed at adapting to circumstances and presupposing a formed ability to use certain means to overcome emotional stress. When choosing active actions, the likelihood of eliminating the effects of stressors on the individual increases. The features of this skill are associated with the "I-concept", empathy, environmental conditions. [1,241]

According to the ideas of A. Maslow, coping behavior is opposed to expressive behavior [2,117]. He characterized coping behavior as a purposeful and motivated action resulting from learning. He also argued that coping is largely determined by external variables that are determined by the environment. Coping behavior involves students making certain efforts and using certain means, and its goal is to satisfy a need or reduce a threat. Coping is more manageable (suppressed, restrained, repressed), since it is typically conscious.

Currently, there are three approaches to interpreting the concept of "coping". The first approach interprets it in terms of dynamics. Ego is one of the methods of psychological defense used to relieve stress. This approach cannot be called widespread primarily because there are supporters who tend to identify coping with its result. The second defines coping in terms of personality traits, as a relatively constant predisposition to respond to stressful events in a certain way. And finally, according to the third approach, coping should be understood as a process, the specificity of which is determined not only by the situation, but also by the stage of development of the conflict, the subject's collision with the outside world. [3,27]

There are various types of coping strategies that are determined by the specifics of stressful situations and individual characteristics of a person, the peculiarities of his cognitive response and behavior in a stressful situation. Attempts have been made to classify these strategies according to a number of features. According to the leading expert in the field of coping styles, R. Lazarus despite significant individual diversity of behavior under stress, there are two global types of students' response style to stress[4,202].

Problem-oriented style, aimed at rational analysis of the problem, is associated with the creation of a plan for resolving the difficult situation and is manifested in such forms of behavior as independent analysis of what happened, asking for help from others, searching for additional information.

Subject-oriented style is a consequence of an emotional response to the situation that is not accompanied by specific actions, and is manifested in attempts not to think about the problem at all, involving others in one's experiences, the desire to forget oneself in sleep,

dissolving one's troubles in alcohol, or compensating for negative emotions with food. These forms of behavior are characterized by a naive, infantile assessment of what is happening.

Overcoming stress can be considered from the standpoint of operational and preventive effects on a stressful situation and a person's reaction to it. Let's take a student's insufficient preparation for classes and a poor result at the exam. Rapid coping with stress involves an attempt to eliminate or reduce the reaction to the stressor, awareness of what has happened; preventive coping consists of preventing the influence of the stressor either by changing the cognitive assessment when perceiving the demands of the situation, or by increasing resistance to the effects of stress. Preventive coping includes such methods as: avoiding stressors by regulating living and working conditions, adequate attitude to issues of preparing a student for each lesson, seminar, survey; optimizing the level of demands of the situation on a person; changing behavior that causes stress; developing personal resources to overcome stress.

In the operational overcoming of stress, the following classes of behavior can be distinguished:

control over the influencing stressors and signs of stress, assessing the situation and choosing an adequate, individually preferred behavior strategy; "attacking" stressors, i.e. determining the possibility of directly eliminating stressors (solving a problem, searching for missing information, etc.); organization of resources, mobilization of effective efforts to overcome stress;

tolerance of the impact of stressors, increasing resistance to them through cognitive reassessment of their perceived significance, volitional efforts, etc.; reducing mental tension through the use of state correction methods.

P. Wong and his colleagues developed a concept for overcoming stress that includes preventive, self-transforming, existential and spiritual strategies - active human reactions that depend on one's ability to symbolize, predict, self-reflect, spiritual manifestation, self-development and self-improvement [1,79].

The classification of stress overcoming strategies ("coping") developed by L.I. Antsyferova is based on the characteristics of the cognitive and behavioral level of regulation of this process and the uniqueness of difficult life and work situations. She identified transformative strategies, methods of adaptation to difficult situations, auxiliary methods of self-preservation, "metastrategic techniques" of life, and methods of improving the moral principles of the individual. The author notes that "coping is a process in which at different stages the subject uses various strategies, sometimes even combining them. At the same time... there are no strategies that would be effective in all difficult situations" [5,16]. It is necessary and possible to teach students to cope with life's difficulties when entering a university, but the student himself decides which methods to use, based on his individual psychological characteristics, life experience, the significance of events, and other factors. I.G. Malkina-Pykh in her works identified three main criteria by which all classifications of coping behavior strategies are built:

1. Emotional/problematic:
2. Cognitive/behavioral:
3. Successful/unsuccessful:

It seems that each coping strategy used by a person can be assessed by all the above criteria, if only because a person who finds himself in a difficult situation can use one or several coping strategies. Thus, it can be assumed that there is a relationship between those personal techniques with the help of which a person forms his attitude to life's difficulties, and what strategy of behavior under stress (coping with the situation) he chooses.

Our students of the 21st century have enormous resources of information, they are able to solve many problems during their studies at university independently, but they do not always consider it necessary and important to do so. They resort to the help of family, friends and teachers or tutors when stressful situations arise. Various strategies can be used for this. They are described below.

Transformative strategies. Some people prefer to use practical actions in the form of searching for a rational way out of a difficult situation, attracting additional information, changing the subjective significance of the features of the situation, using mental self-regulation skills, etc., as well as verbal forms of response to overcome stress, influencing, for example, the subjective source of the conflict situation by the power of persuasion, explanation. The adaptive significance of the strategy of anticipatory coping is great, thanks to which the occurrence of a difficult situation is anticipated, psychological readiness to meet a negative event is formed, or a search for ways to prevent it is undertaken [5,63]

Many events in students' new lives are stressful because they include elements that they are often insufficiently prepared to handle. V. Avdeev [6,59] suggested that people who are confident in their ability to solve a particular problem are more effective in creatively analyzing difficult situations. In this case, the success of solving the problem can, through a feedback mechanism, increase confidence in their ability to overcome stress.

This problem solving strategy can be attributed to the cognitive-behavioral process and the provision of adaptive ways of responding to problems. Their solution is conditioned by the presence of the following abilities and skills: 1) to recognize and understand the content of the problem; 2) to create alternative situations; 3) to conceptualize relevant means of achieving the goal; 4) to foresee the consequences of the decision made; 5) to implement the decision made about the nature of behavior; 6) to independently control behavior and change the decision and goals. The success of implementing the listed components of problem solving is the basis for the manifestation of "self-efficacy". The strategy of rationalization consists in transforming information related to the awareness and use of knowledge only about that part of reality that reflects the most complex and traumatic events of life. Rationalization is behavior when a person does not avoid meeting the threat, but neutralizes it, interpreting it in a painless, advantageous way for himself. As R.M. Granovskaya notes, "the main feature of rationalization is an attempt to create harmony post factum between the desired and real situation and thereby prevent the loss of self-respect. This is an attempt to explain one's behavior that is not confirmed by an objective analysis of the situation, or an attempt to justify the failure to achieve a goal" [7,28]. The reasons for this or that behavior realized as a result of rationalization are based on a combination of distorted information and data reflecting the real situation. Such information creates in a person an unfounded confidence in its adequacy to the true situation and an erroneous idea of one's own behavior as well-controlled and not contradicting objective circumstances.

Strategies for coping with difficult situations. One way to adapt to a difficult situation is to consciously change one's attitude toward it. A person can convince oneself of the existence of positive outcomes in a difficult situation by giving it a special meaning, sometimes not following from its features. A number of personality traits (shyness, anxiety, lack of determination, sensitivity, increased suggestibility, etc.) can contribute to the development of severe experiences, which determines the difficulty of overcoming stress.

Personal adaptation to a difficult situation is a change in the student's role position, acceptance of a certain role and subsequent behavior in accordance with the chosen role (strategy for changing personal qualities).

Conclusion

Overcoming difficult life situations is ensured by the mobilization of personal resources, which are manifested in certain coping strategies and cognitive actions. The nature of these strategies largely depends on personal characteristics, life experience and other psychological factors that determine the individual uniqueness of the difficulties overcoming process. Therefore, it can be assumed that there is a relationship between the personal constructs with which a person forms his attitude to life's difficulties, and the strategy of behavior under stress (coping with the situation) he chooses.

The following most preferred coping strategy was identified: planning a solution to the problem. To a lesser extent, students use such a type of coping strategy as escape-avoidance. This indicates that students in difficult life situations try to somehow regulate, solve them, and not resort to avoiding the problem. They also resort to a lesser extent to the coping strategy of distancing, showing researchers that only a certain part of students try to make cognitive efforts to separate themselves from a difficult situation and reduce its significance. This shows us that most students use transformative behavior strategies, try to cope with difficult life situations, and not separate themselves from them.

The content of the article gives us practical material for further study of the problem of coping strategy. This creates a theoretical basis for practical activities aimed at further studying coping strategies in students of different specialties. Besides that, the study of coping strategies makes a significant contribution to the study of stress resistance, and also allows us to expand our understanding of the subjective aspects of the personality of students.

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